

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPORTANCE OF MATTER OF STRESS STRUGGLE IN SCHOOL STUDENTS AND SHARE OF PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *This article shows all the factors that affect the development of the child to support the psychological and physical health of school students in the learning process. The aim of the article is to assess the importance of stress factors, poor nutrition and low physical activity for the health of school children.*

Keywords: *stress, health of school students, depression, physical activity, academic development, irrational eating.*

Today, the concept of stress is very common and is used in different contexts. A large amount of information, the accelerated rhythm of life in today's modern world can cause a stressful situation. The most difficult thing to cope with such burdens is that it can happen to children, especially during adolescence. During this period, the active formation of the personality takes place, the child reacts sharply to events caused by dangerous problems related to the school and the environment under the strong influence of stress. The health of the schoolchild is the basis of the self-development of the ego, and any change in the child's psychological or physical condition hinders his learning, that is, the process of socialization.

It is not difficult to imagine that the impact of stress on the younger generation can be increased by unfavorable environmental conditions, smoking, lack of physical salt, increased activity, and some additional factors. An unfavorable combination of these factors can lead to serious mental and physiological diseases.

Studies confirm that stress is the cause of various diseases, because human organs stop working normally during stress. Therefore, in order to reduce the risk of developing diseases in the population, it is necessary to recognize the importance of studying stress, to pay special attention to stress in schoolchildren, so that it limits this risk and increases the probability of disease from an early age.

The importance of stress in the context of the organism's physiological reactions to an external stimulus was first emphasized by the American physiologist U. Cannon. It is believed that stress is the body's response to some threatening effect (irritant). According to V. Cannon, a sign of stress was a change in the homeostatic balance in the body.

The Canadian scientist G. Sele founded a new classic theory of stress, which he defined as the body's uncharacteristic rocket in response to any unpleasant impact. G. Sele was the first to associate stress with the complex process of adapting the body to the conditions of the surrounding world.[1]

The full extent of stress is inevitable as the body naturally adapts, but it is important to understand that stress can be both positive and negative. As noted in the studies conducted by D. A. Zhukov, Doctor of Biological Sciences, acute stress activates adaptive reactions, and not long-term stress, but brings an allostatic load to regulatory systems, which causes biological

changes that weaken adaptive processes. With long-term stress, a person's adaptation to the external environment decreases. At the same time, as D. Zhukov pointed out, the perception and assessment of stress depends on the specific aspects of the idea of external or internal stimuli, average or mediating personal characteristics, emotional state and methods, and physiological may not have been.

Recently, more and more researchers are considering possible ways to eliminate the negative effects of stress on the physical and psychological health of a person. In particular, medical-prophylactic and pedagogical monitoring of stress-causing factors in schoolchildren, students, and professionals is being conducted. As a result of similar results, the interaction of stress levels on human physical activity [2], as well as the susceptibility to addictive behaviors due to the transmission of stress, have been studied. Such an important condition for resistance to stress and the ability to overcome it is the support of family and parents.

Among the facts that pose a serious threat to the health of young people, obesity is of great importance. Research literature has noted a link between school-age obesity and stress. A meta-analysis of the relationship between childhood obesity and depression conducted by foreign authors made it possible to draw a clear conclusion that obese children and adolescents suffer more from depression and depressive symptoms [3].

Thus, summarizing the above, it can be confirmed that stress has a complex psycho-emotional and physiological nature and can have a negative impact on the student's health through direct and indirect factors.

In connection with the above, the purpose of the study is to assess the importance of stress factors, poor nutrition and low physical activity for the health of schoolchildren.

Research methodology:

In order to assess the significance of the impact of stress and factors affecting it on the health of 11-12-year-old schoolchildren, a survey was conducted among schoolchildren. The questionnaire contains questions describing the psychological state of the child, his physical activity, his attitude to harmful benefits and the rationality of eating. The total number of test subjects was 341 12-year-old schoolchildren.

General theoretical, empirical and statistical methods are used in the work. The study is based on the scientific literature on the problem of stress in school-aged children, as well as sources containing statistical information on the subject under study. The methods used in the research are linear distribution analysis, two-dimensional analysis of random tables, cluster analysis. Special SPSS Statistics 21.0 software was used for statistical analysis. Tadqiqot natijalari:

According to the results of the study, more than half of the cases (54%) have symptoms of depression, 46% of children have no symptoms of depression.

The level of depression in schoolchildren

Level of Depression	All of them, %
depression (subdepression)	30.3
middle depression	15.7
hard depression (middle stress)	5.6
The hardest depression	2.4

no symptoms of depression	46
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The analysis of the results of the questionnaire showed that the majority of children of this age do not maintain a healthy lifestyle. 79% of children are at risk, so 4/5 of them are at risk of developing the disease. Among the risk factors, irrational eating (76%), high cholesterol (33%) and overweight (28.7%) prevail, which threaten the health of adolescents from the cardiovascular system.

The statistical analysis of the results of the survey showed that 74% of students evaluate the importance of rational nutrition as the basis of a healthy lifestyle. As noted in some foreign studies, food, especially hyperpalatable (for example, high in fat and sugar), can have addictive properties. Stress is an important factor in the development of addiction and addiction relapse, and in exchange can increase the risk of obesity and other diseases. Uncontrolled stress alters eating patterns, the nature and consumption of hyperplasia, thus altering the allostatic load over time and inducing neurobiological adaptations that can cope with anything.

This experiment, among other similar studies, shows that high-intensity aerobic exercise increases resistance and has a positive effect on well-being in an adolescent population.

Controlling the level of stress in children's lives, as well as maintaining a healthy diet and adequate physical activity, is the basis of academic success. The results of research conducted by American scientists have shown that there is a direct relationship between a healthy lifestyle and the minimum amount of stress in schoolchildren and academic success.

Summary

Based on the statistical analysis of the research data, the authors concluded that there are significant physiological and psychological deviations in the health indicators of schoolchildren: cholesterol level, blood pressure, stress indicators, depression, depression, depression, disease. Based on the questionnaire data, the authors confirmed that children know the need for a healthy lifestyle, but not all of them follow it.

The presented statistics (Table 1) indicate that there are significant physiological and psychological disorders in the health of schoolchildren in all studied indicators: cholesterol level, arterial active gastric ulcer, obesity. The analysis of the questionnaire data allows to emphasize that children know the need for a healthy lifestyle, but not all of them follow it. In this regard, we believe that it is necessary to carry out medical and preventive work on the correction of disorders in the health of schoolchildren.

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